

Health Literacy and Attitudinal Dynamics in Maternal Health Service Utilisation: A Study of Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA) in Urban Slums of Kolkata Municipal Corporation

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Abstract

Maternal health behaviours are dependent on a mother's level of health literacy, which can either enable or hinder care-seeking, particularly in low-socioeconomic-status urban slum settings where access to comprehensive and timely antenatal care (ANC) services is often inadequate. Although the Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA) offers free and inclusive ANC services across India, utilisation among pregnant women residing in the Kolkata Municipal Corporation (KMC) slums remains limited.

A community-based mixed methods cross-sectional study was conducted among mothers who had delivered within the previous year to assess their understanding of ANC benefits, awareness of danger signs during pregnancy, and knowledge of PMSMA, supplemented by qualitative interviews exploring perceptions, barriers, and facilitators of care-seeking.

Findings indicated that PMSMA awareness was generally high, especially among women aged 20–35 years (94.44%), those with higher educational levels (97.4%), and those living in joint families (100%), while household income showed no significant association. ANC utilisation, however, varied considerably by education: primary-educated women demonstrated better adherence (42.9% attending more than four visits), whereas women with higher secondary education or above were more likely to participate in fewer visits (83.3% attending only one to two visits). Attitudinal measures showed improvement with increasing PMSMA exposure. However, all women with no PMSMA visits were unaware of its purpose (100%), those with more than four visits recognised benefits such as early detection of complications (44.2%) and safeguarding fetal health (53.3%). Perceived helpfulness and satisfaction also rose with utilisation, with 31.3% of high-utilisation women rating services as “very helpful” and 33.3% as “very satisfied,” compared to universal dissatisfaction among non-users. Preference for private facilities increased with greater ANC engagement.

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Women in joint families demonstrated the highest awareness, supported by intergenerational guidance, stronger information-sharing networks, and collective decision-making. Overall, inadequate maternal health literacy emerged as a key barrier to optimal PMSMA utilisation. Strengthening culturally sensitive community-based awareness initiatives and enhancing provider communication are critical to improving ANC uptake in urban slum environments.

Keywords: *Health Literacy, Maternal Health, Utilization, PMSMA, Urban Slums, Kolkata.*

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Introduction

Health literacy is a critical determinant of maternal health, enabling individuals and communities to understand, evaluate, and act upon health information to make informed decisions (Coughlin, 2020). Pregnant women living in urban slums constitute a high-risk population with constrained access to essential health services. Unsafe maternal health practices are commonly observed in these settings, and multiple barriers to service utilization have been widely reported. Even within the same city, slum communities often display considerable variation in health indicators and patterns of healthcare use. This study explores the presence of hazardous maternal care practices and examines differences in the utilisation of maternal health services between two distinct slum areas. (Khan, 2012).

India has made considerable progress in strengthening maternal healthcare through national initiatives aimed at reducing preventable maternal and neonatal deaths. The Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA), launched in 2016, is a key programme designed to provide comprehensive antenatal care (ANC) to all pregnant women, particularly those in underserved areas. Under PMSMA, free ANC services are offered on the 9th of every month, including clinical examinations, haemoglobin estimation, blood pressure measurement, blood sugar testing, and other essential diagnostics. The programme also provides iron and folic acid supplementation, nutritional counselling, birth preparedness advice, and timely referral for high-risk pregnancies. By facilitating early detection and management of maternal complications, PMSMA seeks to prevent adverse pregnancy outcomes among vulnerable women. (PMSMA, 2016).

For women living in urban slums, PMSMA is especially important due to persistent inequities in healthcare access and information. Misconceptions about pregnancy, cultural practices, lack of awareness of entitlements, and inadequate health literacy often prevent women from availing free ANC services. Low health literacy may limit recognition of danger signs, reduce adherence to scheduled ANC visits, and delay care-seeking during complications. Conversely, women with higher levels of health literacy

are more likely to value regular check-ups, follow medical advice, and make informed decisions about pregnancy care. (Dubey, 2021).

Developing health literacy requires more than the dissemination of information; it involves strengthening women's skills, confidence, and ability to navigate the healthcare system. Through structured counselling and educational interactions, PMSMA has the potential to empower women with essential knowledge on nutrition, hygiene, complication recognition, and the need for prompt medical attention. (Tavananezhad, 2022).

The present study examines the influence of health literacy on the utilisation of PMSMA services among pregnant women residing in the urban slums under the Kolkata Municipal Corporation. It explores service-use patterns, barriers to uptake, and levels of maternal health knowledge, to generate evidence to inform policies and programmes that enhance maternal healthcare access for disadvantaged urban populations.

Objectives of the Study

- To determine the association between key socio-demographic variables and the level of awareness regarding the Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA) among pregnant women in urban slums.
- To examine the quality of PMSMA service delivery and identify the barriers and perceived facilitators influencing the effective utilization of antenatal check-ups.
- To evaluate the attitudinal dynamics—including perceived importance, helpfulness, and satisfaction—that influence the frequency of Antenatal Care (ANC) attendance and the overall acceptance of PMSMA services among the target population.

Materials and Methods

Study Design

A community-based mixed methods cross-sectional study was carried out in the urban slums of the Kolkata Municipal Corporation, West Bengal, utilizing quantitative survey data and qualitative focus group discussions (FGDs) to achieve a deeper understanding of the barriers and facilitators to PMSMA utilization.

Study Area

Selected urban slums of the Kolkata Municipal Corporation (KMC) in West Bengal

Study Population

Mothers who had delivered within one year of the date of the study were included in the study. Non-consenting participants and mothers who had registered under PMSMA within the last 3 months from the date of the study were excluded from being selected as participants.

Sample

Data was collected from a total of 100 participants. A convenience sampling technique was employed to select mothers as study participants. The inclusion criteria consisted of mothers who had delivered within one year of the date of the study, were registered

at Anganwadi centres, and had availed antenatal care (ANC) services in the selected study area.

Procedures

Data collection was carried out over a period of 20 days. Before participation, informed consent was obtained from all mothers involved in the study. A semi-structured interview schedule was employed to gather socio-demographic information, while a checklist was utilized to assess the utilization of antenatal services under the Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA).

The interview technique served as the primary method for collecting data directly from the mothers. To ensure accuracy and reliability, all collected information was cross-verified with records available at the Urban Primary Health Centre (UPHC) and further corroborated with details provided by ASHA workers responsible for the respective areas.

In addition to individual interviews, qualitative methods were employed to gain deeper insights. A total of 20 in-depth interviews and 5 focus group discussions were conducted with service providers and women of reproductive age groups. These interactions helped capture nuanced perspectives on service delivery and utilization, complementing the quantitative data collected during the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Mothers who had delivered within one year of the date of the study were included in the study and enrolled during pregnancy for the PMSMA entitlements
- All the service providers associated with the PMSMA Service delivery were included in the study
- Individuals residing in the same location for at least 6 months.

Exclusion Criteria

- Migrant pregnant women who have relocated to the area within the past 6 months.
- Women with severe mental or physical disabilities that may hinder effective communication.
- Service providers who have joined the clinic within the last 3 months.
- Any individuals unwilling to provide informed consent for the study.

Ethical Considerations

Permission was taken from the Urban Local Bodies (ULB) to conduct the Study in their location of Urban Slums of Kolkata.

Data Analysis

For the quantitative analysis, descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, and mean were computed, along with inferential tests including Chi-square and t-test. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 26 software to ensure accuracy and reliability. For the qualitative component, thematic analysis was conducted using NVivo software and manual coding techniques to identify recurring patterns and themes from the interviews and focus group discussions. The findings from both quantitative and qualitative strands were integrated using a convergent mixed-method

approach, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the research objectives by triangulating data from multiple sources.

Results

Table 1. Association between Utilization of PMSMA among Mothers with Their Selected Socio-Demographic Variables

Variable	Categories	Heard About Check-ups (%)	Not Heard (%)	p-value
Age Group	Below 15	0 (0.0)	18 (100.0)	< .001
	15–19	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	
	20–34	90 (94.4)	5 (5.6)	
	35+	6 (75.0)	2 (25.0)	
Education Level	No formal education	6 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	< .005
	Primary school	44 (89.8)	5 (10.2)	
	High school	38 (97.4)	1 (2.6)	
	Higher secondary or beyond	5 (83.3)	1 (16.7)	
Family Type	Missing/Other	0 (0.0)	18 (100.0)	< .001
	Nuclear	59 (89.4)	7 (10.6)	
	Joint	34 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	
	Missing/Other	0 (0.0)	18 (100.0)	
Family Income Adequacy	Facing challenges	61 (93.8)	4 (6.2)	< .002
	Not facing challenges	32 (91.4)	3 (8.6)	
	Missing/Other	0 (0.0)	18 (100.0)	

The survey of 100 mothers revealed that awareness of the Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA) was generally high across most socio-demographic groups. Women aged 20–35 years demonstrated the highest level of awareness, with 94.44% reporting knowledge of the program, whereas awareness was comparatively lower among those younger than 20 years and older than 35 years. Educational attainment showed a strong positive association with awareness: 89.8% of participants who had completed primary schooling were aware of PMSMA, and this proportion increased to 97.4% among women with higher secondary education or beyond. Family structure also influenced awareness significantly. All women from joint families (34 participants, 100%) reported knowledge of PMSMA, while awareness was slightly lower among women from nuclear families, where 59 participants (89.4%) were informed about the program. In contrast, household income did not appear to be a major determinant of awareness, as knowledge of PMSMA was broadly similar across different income categories. These findings suggest that age, education, and family structure play a more critical role in shaping awareness of maternal health programs than economic status.

Table 2. Relationship between Awareness of PMSMA and Various Aspects of Service Utilization and Quality during Antenatal Check-Ups

Variables	Categories	Heard about PMSMA (Yes)	Heard about PMSMA (No)	n (%)	p-value
Received food items	Yes	33 (91.7%)	0 (0.0%)	36 (30.5%)	<0.001
	No	60 (93.8%)	0 (0.0%)	64 (54.2%)	

after PMSMA check-up	Never attended / Not applicable	0 (0.0%)	18 (100.0%)	18 (15.3%)	
The doctor/nurse talked about diet, health, or the baby's growth	Yes, detailed advice	47 (94.0%)	0 (0.0%)	50 (42.4%)	<0.001
	Yes, but only briefly	37 (94.9%)	0 (0.0%)	39 (33.1%)	
	No, they didn't	9 (81.8%)	0 (0.0%)	11 (9.3%)	
	Never attended / Not applicable	0 (0.0%)	18 (100.0%)	18 (15.3%)	
Frequency of ASHA/ANM visits	Sometimes (monthly)	15 (88.2%)	0 (0.0%)	17 (14.4%)	<0.001
	Rarely (a few months)	60 (95.2%)	0 (0.0%)	63 (53.4%)	
	Never	18 (90.0%)	0 (0.0%)	20 (16.9%)	
	Never attended / Not applicable	0 (0.0%)	18 (100.0%)	18 (15.3%)	
Perceived helpfulness of monthly check-ups	Yes, very helpful	18 (94.7%)	0 (0.0%)	19 (16.1%)	<0.001
	Yes, but it could be improved	74 (92.5%)	0 (0.0%)	80 (67.8%)	
	No, not helpful	1 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (0.8%)	
	Never attended / Not applicable	0 (0.0%)	18 (100.0%)	18 (15.3%)	
Difficulties faced during check-ups Proper conduct of medical tests (blood/urine)	Had to wait long	34 (91.9%)	0 (0.0%)	37 (31.4%)	<0.001
	Far away & long wait	32 (97.0%)	0 (0.0%)	33 (28.0%)	
	Clinic far	1 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (1.7%)	
	No difficulty	25 (92.6%)	0 (0.0%)	27 (22.9%)	
	Didn't know about the check-up	1 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	1 (0.8%)	
	Never attended / Not applicable	0 (0.0%)	18 (100.0%)	18 (15.3%)	
	Yes, all tests were done properly	3 (75.0%)	0 (0.0%)	4 (3.4%)	<0.001
	Yes, but skipped some tests	88 (93.6%)	0 (0.0%)	94 (79.7%)	
	No tests performed	2 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	2 (1.7%)	
	Never attended / Not applicable	0 (0.0%)	18 (100.0%)	18 (15.3%)	

The analysis explores the association between the educational qualifications of participants and their tendency to attend Antenatal Care (ANC) check-ups during pregnancy. The findings reveal notable variations in ANC utilization across different educational levels. Among women with no formal education, only one participant (16.7%) reported attending one to two ANC visits, while the majority, five participants (83.3%), attended more than four visits, indicating that even without formal education, some women adhered to recommended ANC practices. Women with primary education showed a more balanced pattern, with 24.5% attending one to two visits, 32.7% attending three to four visits, and 42.9% attending more than four visits, suggesting that basic education may positively influence ANC awareness and compliance. In contrast, women who completed high school were more likely to have fewer visits, with 48.7% attending one to two visits, 30.8% attending three to four visits, and only 20.5% attending more than four visits. Interestingly, among those with education beyond high school, ANC attendance was markedly low, as 83.3% reported only one to two visits, 16.7% attended three to four visits, and none attended more than four visits. Overall, across all educational categories, 37% of participants attended

one to two ANC visits, 29% attended three to four visits, and 34% reported more than four visits. These findings suggest that while education generally enhances awareness of ANC, higher educational attainment does not necessarily translate into greater compliance, highlighting the need for targeted interventions across all educational groups.

Table 3. Maternal Attitudes and Perceptions in Relation to Utilization of PMSMA

Parameter	Category	Response Option	n (%)
1. Number of PMSMA Visits & importance of attending PMSMA	0 visits	don't know	18 (100)
	1–2 visits	Not useful	3 (30)
		Detect problems early	12 (27.9)
		Detect problems early & not useful	9 (56.3)
		Detect problems early & ensure baby is healthy	6 (40)
	3–4 visits	Not useful	4 (40)
		Detect problems early	12 (27.9)
	>4 visits	Ensure the baby's health	1 (100)
		Detect problems early	19 (44.2)
		Detect problems early & ensure baby is healthy	8 (53.3)
2. Number of ANC Visits & Preferred Place for ANC Check-ups	0 visits	Both govt. & private facilities	18 (100)
	1–2 visits	Govt. hospitals	13 (48.1)
		Private clinics	24 (32.9)
	3–4 visits	Govt. hospitals	6 (22.2)
		Private clinics	23 (31.5)
	>4 visits	Govt. hospitals	8 (29.6)
		Private clinics	26 (35.6)
	3. Number of ANC Visits & Perceived Helpfulness of ANC Visits	0 visits	Not much
1–2 visits		very helpful	31 (38.8)
3–4 visits			24 (30.0)
>4 visits			25 (31.3)
4. Number of ANC Visits & Perceived Helpfulness of PMSMA Services	0 visits	Not helpful	18 (100)
	1–2 visits		37 (37.4)
	3–4 visits		29 (29.3)
	>4 visits		34 (33.3)
		Helpful	
5. Number of ANC Visits & Satisfaction with PMSMA Services	0 visits	Needs improvement	18 (100)
	1–2 visits	Neutral	17 (35.4)
		Very satisfied	20 (36.1)
	3–4 visits	Neutral	13 (27.1)
		Very satisfied	16 (30.6)
	>4 visits	Neutral	18 (37.5)
		Very satisfied	16 (33.3)

The analysis of maternal attitudes showed clear differences across levels of PMSMA and ANC use, highlighting how exposure to these services affects perceptions and motivations. Among women who had not attended any PMSMA visits, all participants (18; 100%) reported being unaware of the program's purpose, indicating a complete lack of understanding of its goals. In contrast, women who attended 1–2 PMSMA visits showed a shift toward health-focused reasoning, with the most common motivation being early detection of pregnancy-related complications (12; 27.9%), while a significant portion (9; 56.3%) mentioned multiple reasons, such as early detection and ensuring the baby's health. This pattern became even stronger among women with

more than four PMSMA visits, where early detection (19; 44.2%) and protecting the baby's health (8; 53.3%) were the main motivators. These results suggest that repeated exposure to PMSMA services increases awareness and promotes preventive health behaviours.

Preferences for ANC check-up locations also varied by utilization level. Women who had not attended any ANC visits expressed equal preference for both public and private facilities (18; 100%). Among those with 1–2 visits, nearly half (48.1%) favoured government hospitals, whereas women with 3–4 visits and those with more than four visits showed an increasing inclination toward private clinics (31.5% and 35.6%, respectively). This pattern may reflect a growing emphasis on perceived quality and personalized care as women engage more frequently with maternal health services.

Perceptions of helpfulness exhibited a clear positive association with ANC utilization. All women with no ANC visits considered the services “not much” helpful, while the majority of those with 1–2 visits (31; 38.8%), 3–4 visits (24; 30.0%), and more than four visits (25; 31.3%) rated ANC as “very helpful.” A similar trend was observed for PMSMA services: women with no ANC visits unanimously reported PMSMA as “not helpful” (18; 100%), whereas helpfulness was acknowledged by women with 1–2 visits (37; 37.4%), 3–4 visits (29; 29.3%), and more than four visits (34; 33.3%). Satisfaction levels mirrored these patterns, with all women who had no ANC visits feeling that PMSMA services required improvement (18; 100%). Among women with 1–2 ANC visits, 20 (36.1%) expressed being “very satisfied,” a proportion that remained relatively stable among those with 3–4 visits (16; 30.6%) and more than four visits (16; 33.3%). Neutral responses were common across all utilization categories, suggesting that while satisfaction improves with greater engagement, there remains scope for enhancing service quality and addressing unmet expectations.

Discussion

According to the National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), 58.1% of women in India attended at least four antenatal care (ANC) visits. In comparison, ANC utilization under the Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA) in the present study was slightly lower, at 54%, within the study areas. As per reports from October 2025, the top five performing states in terms of the number of pregnant women in their second or third trimester receiving ANC under PMSMA were Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, and West Bengal. PMSMA provides a standardized package of antenatal care services—including essential investigations and medications—on the 9th of every month at designated public health facilities such as PHCs, CHCs, district hospitals, and urban health centres in both urban and rural settings. These services complement the routine ANC offered at health facilities and outreach sites.

This study evaluates mothers' knowledge of PMSMA in relation to their socio-demographic characteristics, examines the influence of educational qualifications on ANC attendance, and explores maternal attitudes and perceptions associated with PMSMA utilization. Awareness of PMSMA was high across most socio-demographic groups, with women aged 20–35 years demonstrating the highest levels of awareness. Family structure also played a role, with joint families positively influencing awareness. Maternal attitudes improved with greater exposure to PMSMA and ANC services. Women with no PMSMA visits lacked understanding of its purpose, whereas those with more visits commonly recognized benefits such as early detection of

complications and ensuring the baby's health. Perceived helpfulness and satisfaction with both ANC and PMSMA services increased with utilization. Women who had not attended ANC visits considered the services unhelpful and in need of improvement, while those with higher visit frequencies consistently reported greater helpfulness and higher satisfaction. Enhance the number of PMSMA clinics, as recommended by mothers, to alleviate issues of time constraints and crowding. Institutionalize the roles of ASHA/ANM workers to align with the steady community involvement. Mandatory Male Involvement for Implementing targeted education sessions for husbands to transform spousal indifference into shared responsibility, addressing domestic obstacles to participation.

Evidence from previous studies supports these findings. A cross-sectional study conducted in rural Belagavi among 161 participants found that most were aged 20–30 years, and awareness levels were significantly associated with family type, with similar patterns observed across different structures (Sinha, 2019). Another study revealed a positive association between higher quality of ANC and greater utilization, particularly in rural areas, emphasizing that poor-quality care reduces ANC uptake and highlighting the need for policy measures (Ran, 2008). Similarly, a study in urban slums of Bhubaneswar Smart City reported that awareness and utilization of PMSMA remain suboptimal even after six years of implementation. Socio-demographic factors—especially education, occupation, socio-economic status, and religion—strongly influence both awareness and utilization. Lower utilization among disadvantaged groups underscores persistent inequities in access to ANC. Fixed-day service delivery under PMSMA may limit convenience for some mothers, suggesting the need for improved outreach and flexibility (De, 2022). Other studies confirm that ANC utilization is significantly associated with age, religion, socio-economic class, education, and caste, and recommend enhanced efforts to improve awareness and timely ANC interventions to reduce maternal mortality (Kakati, 2016; Prajapati, 2022).

Awareness of health schemes plays a critical role in improving maternal health outcomes. Ensuring that pregnant women receive essential ANC components—such as weight monitoring, blood pressure and abdominal examination, urine and blood tests, and supplementation with iron–folic acid and calcium—can substantially reduce maternal and child health complications (Dandona, 2022). Initiatives like PMSMA facilitate early identification of preventable risk factors and contribute to reducing maternal mortality in India. Focused and well-designed educational interventions can further strengthen awareness, shape positive maternal attitudes, and encourage optimal utilization of available healthcare services (Prajapati A. K., 2022).

Several studies have shown that improving attitudes toward health programs requires engaging with community members, particularly men and other key decision-makers. Initiatives that involve local community leaders, health workers, and male family members in health education have been more successful in increasing program uptake (Sarkar et al., 2020). Additionally, public health campaigns that use local languages, cultural narratives, and community influencers can effectively change negative perceptions about government health services.

Conclusion

Higher awareness of PMSMA among women in joint families can be linked to strong support systems and intergenerational knowledge sharing. Elderly members often guide maternal health practices and promote government schemes within the

household. Joint families also have greater social interactions and community engagement, which help spread health-related information. Collective decision-making further prioritizes maternal health, encouraging compliance with programs like PMSMA. In contrast, nuclear families may lack these networks, leading to lower awareness.

Policy Recommendations:

To improve maternal health outcomes in urban slums, targeted interventions must focus on strengthening health literacy and addressing attitudinal barriers. Community-based awareness programs through ASHA workers and Anganwadi centres should be scaled up, using local language IEC materials and digital platforms for better outreach. Incorporating health literacy modules into existing maternal health schemes and promoting peer-support groups can empower women to make informed decisions. Additionally, regular monitoring and feedback mechanisms should be implemented to ensure effective utilization of PMSMA services and timely identification of high-risk pregnancies.

Limitations

Since the interview method was used, it was difficult to collect data, and respondents faced issues in recalling their service intakes. As the study was self-funded, henceforth couldn't collect data from all the slums of Kolkata due to resource constraints.

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Conflicts of interest

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References

- Agarwal, S., & Taneja, S. (2021). Health literacy and maternal health care utilisation in low-income urban areas: A review. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*, 46(2), 243–248.
- Bhattacharyya, S., Issac, A., Rajbangshi, P., & Srivastava, A. (2020). “Every ninth day”: Implementation of PMSMA programme in India—A qualitative assessment. *Reproductive Health*, 17(1), 1–11.

- Coughlin, S. S., Vernon, M., Hatzigeorgiou, C., & George, V. (2020). Health Literacy, Social Determinants of Health, and Disease Prevention and Control. *Journal of environment and health sciences*, 6(1), 3061.
- Dandona, R., Majumder, M., Akbar, M., Bhattacharya, D., Nanda, P., Kumar, G. A., & Dandona, L. (2022). Assessment of quality of antenatal care services in public sector facilities in India. *BMJ Open*, 12(12), e065200. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2022-065200>
- De, M. S., Swain, M. T. R., Nayak, M. S., Sonalika, M. S., & Dash, R. K. (2022). Utilization of antenatal services among mothers under Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan in select urban slums of Bhubaneswar Smart City. *NeuroQuantology*, 20(17), 260–266.
- Dubey, M., Kumar, M. M., Choudhary, Y., & Toppo, M. (2021). *Graduates of MD Community Medicine to specialize in infectious diseases: A long-term public health prospect*. *Indian Journal of Community Medicine*, 46(3), 576–577. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijcm.IJCM_1058_20
- Fleming, L., & Matthews, Z. (2020). Urban slums and maternal health risks: An Indian perspective. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth*, 20(1), 1–12.
- Ghosh, R. (2021). Maternal health care services in urban slums: Evidence from India. *Health & Social Care in the Community*, 29(5), e124–e135.
- International Institute for Population Sciences. (2021). *National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5), India fact sheet 2019–21*. IIPS.
- Jiao, B., Iversen, I., Sato, R., Pecenka, C., Khan, S., Baral, R., Kruk, M. E., Arsenault, C., & Verguet, S. (2024). Association between achieving adequate antenatal care and health-seeking behaviors: A study of Demographic and Health Surveys in 47 low- and middle-income countries. *PLoS medicine*, 21(7), e1004421. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1004421>
- Kakati, R., Barua, K., & Borah, M. (2016). Factors associated with the utilization of antenatal care services in rural areas of Assam, India. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 3(10), 2799–2805. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20163364>
- Khan, Z., Mehnaz, S., Siddiqui, A. R., Ansari, A., Khalil, S., & Sachdeva, S. (2012). All Slums are Not Equal: Maternal Health Conditions Among Two Urban Slum Dwellers. *Indian journal of community medicine: official publication of the Indian Association of Preventive & Social Medicine*, 37(1), 50–56. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0970-0218.94027>
- Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. (2014). *Maternal Health Programme: Annual Report 2013–2014*. Retrieved from <https://main.mohfw.gov.in/sites/default/files/Chapter415.pdf>
- Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. (2016). *Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA): Technical operational guidelines*. Government of India.
- Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. (n.d.). *About the PMSMA scheme*. Retrieved from <https://pmsma.mohfw.gov.in/about-scheme/#about>
- Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. (n.d.). *National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5) Phase II report*. Retrieved from https://mohfw.gov.in/sites/default/files/NFHS-5_Phase-II_0.pdf
- Mohanty, S. K., & Kastor, A. (2017). Urban inequalities in maternal healthcare utilisation in India. *PLOS ONE*, 12(12), e0189287.

- National Health Mission Himachal Pradesh. (n.d.). *PMSMA Guidelines*. Retrieved from <http://www.nrhmp.gov.in/sites/default/files/files/PMSMA-Guidelines.pdf>
- Office of the Registrar General & Census Commissioner, India. (2023). *Sample Registration System (SRS) Maternal Mortality Ratio Bulletin*.
- PMSMA. (2016). *About*. Retrieved from <https://pmsma.nhp.gov.in/about-scheme/>
- Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan (PMSMA). (n.d.). *Gov. in*. Retrieved from [https://www.nhp.gov.in/pradhan-mantri-surakshitmatritva-abhiyan-\(pmsma\)_pg](https://www.nhp.gov.in/pradhan-mantri-surakshitmatritva-abhiyan-(pmsma)_pg)
- Prajapati, A. K., Kumar, V., Soni, K., Singh, N. P., Jain, P. K., & Ruchi. (2022). Prevalence of high-risk pregnancy among pregnant women enrolled under Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan in government health facilities of district Etawah, Uttar Pradesh: A cross-sectional study. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 11(5), 1876–1882. https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpe.jfmpe_1636_21
- Press Information Bureau. (2021). *Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR)*. Retrieved from <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1697441>
- Sample Registration System. (2019). *Special bulletin on maternal mortality in India 2017–2019*. Retrieved from <https://censusindia.gov.in/census.website/data/SRSSMMB>
- Sarkar, S., & Saha, I. (2022). Determinants of antenatal care utilisation among women in an urban slum of Kolkata. *Indian Journal of Public Health*, 66(1), 45–50.
- Sinha, P., Gunagi, P. R., Viveki, R. G., Kamble, M., & Halki, S. (2019). Knowledge of antenatal care among mothers of infants in the rural area of Belagavi: a cross-sectional study. *International Journal Of Community Medicine And Public Health*, 6(11), 4838–4843. <https://doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20195065>
- Sinha, P., Gunagi, P. R., Viveki, R. G., Kamble, M., & Halki, S. (2019). Utilization of antenatal services under Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan in rural areas of North Karnataka: A cross-sectional study. *National Journal of Research in Community Medicine*, 8(2), 184–188. <http://dx.doi.org/10.26727/njrcm.2019.8.2.184-188>
- Super User. (2019). Odisha is among the top 5 states to benefit from Pradhan Mantri Surakshit Matritva Abhiyan. *The Federal*. Retrieved from <https://thefederal.com/health/odisha-among-top-5-states-to-benefit-from-pradhan-mantri-surakshitmatritva-abhiyan/>
- Tavananezhad, N., Bolbanabad, A. M., Ghelichkhani, F., Effati-Daryani, F., & Mirghafourvand, M. (2022). The relationship between health literacy and empowerment in pregnant women: a cross-sectional study. *BMC pregnancy and childbirth*, 22(1), 351. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12884-022-04686-z>
- Vishnu, C. S., Nirgude, A. S., Rajarathnam, A., Navya, N., & Akshaya, K. M. (2019). Do pregnant mothers utilize supplementary nutrition along with other antenatal services? A cross-sectional study from Mangaluru, Karnataka state, India. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*, 6(4), 1614–1619. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18203/2394-6040.ijcmph20191393>
- Wikipedia contributors. (2022). *Prenatal care*. In *Wikipedia*. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Prenatal_care&oldid=1120402316
- World Health Organization. (2016). *WHO recommendations on antenatal care for a positive pregnancy experience*. World Health Organization.

